

Spectrophotometric Studies on Chelate Formation in Iron (II)-4-Isonitroso-1-phenyl-3-methyl-pyrazolone-5-System

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The green complex formed by iron (II) with 4-isonitroso-1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone-5 in acidic medium has been studied spectrophotometrically in 40:60 alcohol-water solutions 0.2M with respect to sodium perchlorate. It has absorption maximum at 630 m μ and optimum pH range from 4.7 to 5.1 in which it is stable for about 2 hrs at room temperature. The results of Job's, slope ratio and molar ratio methods indicate a composition of 1 : 1 for the complex. The stability constant of the complex obtained by Hagenmuller's method using Job's plots is $\log K=3.47$ at room temperature ($\sim 32^\circ$).

Hovorka and Sykora¹ and Dubskey et al² have described reactions of several metal ions with 4-isonitroso-1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone-5. However, the analytical potentialities of this reagent have not been investigated fully. This paper reports the results of spectrophotometric studies of the green coloured solution formed when iron (II) salts (at relatively low concentrations) react with alcoholic solution of 4-isonitroso-1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone-5. It has been found that the green coloured solution is stable for about two hours and shows an absorption maximum at 630 m μ . The intensity of colour remains constant in the pH range between 4.7 and 5.1 provided triply-all glass distilled oxygen free water is used. The nature of the species present in the green solution has been studied using Job's method of continued variations³, slope ratio method⁴ and molar ratio method.⁵ Attempt has been made to evaluate the formation constant of the complex by Hagenmuller's method⁶.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Isonitroso-1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone-5 was prepared by the method of Knorr.⁷ It was twice recrystallised from hot acetic acid to obtain orange crystalline solid (m.p., 157°). The reagent solutions of known concentrations were prepared by dissolving accurately weighed known amounts of the reagent in freshly distilled pure ethanol.

Standard solutions of iron(II) were prepared using ferrous ammonium sulphate (B.D.H., Analar) and triple-distilled oxygen free water. The concentrations of these solutions were checked by gravimetric and volumetric methods.

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Sodium perchlorate (Riedel, Germany) was used to maintain the ionic strength of the mixtures constant.

All absorbance measurements were made on Beckman DU spectrophotometer at room temperature ($\approx 32^\circ$). Measurements of pH were made by Beckman pH meter (Model H2).

Composition of the complex: Mixtures containing 1 : 1, 1:2 and 1:3 ratios of iron (II): reagent in 40 per cent (by volume) of ethanol were prepared and their absorbances were measured at different wavelengths from 400 to 700 $m\mu$. All the mixtures showed maximum absorbance at the same wave length of 630 $m\mu$ thus indicating formation of a single complex⁸. All the subsequent absorbance measurements were carried out at 630 $m\mu$. Neither iron (II) nor reagent showed any appreciable absorption at this wavelength.

Job's method: A series of solutions was prepared using equimolar ($2.0 \times 10^{-3}M$) metal and reagent solutions so as to vary the metal: reagent ratio from 1 : 9 to 9:1. Each solution was made 0.2M with respect to sodium perchlorate and had the solvent composition of 40 per cent ethanol by volume. pH of each mixture was within the optimum range of 4.7—5.1. The absorbance of these solutions was measured against solvent at 600, 630 and 660 $m\mu$. Results obtained at 630 $m\mu$ are shown in Fig. 1 (curve 1). The maximum at 0.5 indicates formation of complex containing iron (II) and the reagent in the ratio of 1 : 1. Similar results were obtained at 600 $m\mu$ and 660 $m\mu$. The same ratio of 1 : 1 was also obtained on repeating the experiment at a different constant molarity ($1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$) of iron (II) and the reagent (curve 2, Fig. 1).

Fig 1 JOB'S METHOD

Slope ratio method: The concentration of the variable component was varied from $5.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{M}$ to $5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{M}$ in presence of the excess concentration of $2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$ of the constant component. The pH of the solutions was within the range 4.7 to 5.1 and ionic strength 0.2M (NaClO_4). Fig. 2 shows the plots of absorbance at 630 m μ against

Fig. 2. SLOPE-RATIO METHOD

1. Fe(II) varying
2. Reagent varying

Fig 3 MOLE-RATIO METHOD

concentration of the variable component. The ratio of slopes of the two lines is found to be unity indicating the 1 : 1 composition of the complex formed in solution.

Molar ratio method: A series of solutions was prepared by adding varying amounts of the reagent to a fixed amount of iron (II) so as to vary the molar ratio of iron (II): reagent from 1:3.33 to 1:0.33. The solutions had a *pH* between 4.7 and 5.1 and were 0.2M with respect to NaClO_4 . The measured absorbance is plotted against the mole ratio of metal: reagent, in Fig. 3. The figure shows a break at mole ratio of unity, confirming the formation of a 1 : 1 complex. However, it may be seen that the break is not sharp in spite of the fact that ionic strength of the solution has been kept constant at 0.2. This might suggest that the complex formed in the system may not be very stable. This is confirmed on evaluating stability constant of the complex by Hagenmuller's method. Using Job's plots of Fig. 1, a value of $\log K = 3.46$ is obtained (at $\sim 32^\circ$).

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